

Unguja Ukuu Amulet Seal

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Entry tags: Amulet, Amulet, Religious Group, Abrahamic, African Religions, Islam, Ritual inscriptions, Arabic, Islamic Traditions, Ritual text, Swahili Religion, Semitic, Prayer, Text, Arabian, Afro-Asiatic, Excavated text, Central Semitic, West Semitic, Language, Standard Arabic, African Religion, Islam in Africa, Swahili Islam, Islam

Archaeological excavations in 2018 at the site of Unguja Ukuu (Zanzibar) yielded a small rock-crystal cabochon amulet seal with the Arabic word "lillah" ("for God") inscribed in the Kufic script on its domed surface. The amulet was discovered in contexts dating to the 8th-9th centuries CE, making it one of the oldest Islamic artifacts discovered thus far that far south along the East African coast. The word inscribed on its surface is the oldest piece of writing thus far recovered from Zanzibar, predating the Kizimkazi Mosque inscription by a few centuries. This amulet seal was likely set in jewelry worn on one's person, as indicated by the faint discoloration visible on the flat surface of the amulet. Examination with Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) revealed that the inscription was made with a rotary tool. At some later point, a diagonal spall was removed across the inscription. At first, the spall was assumed to have been removed on purpose, reflecting a deliberate defacing of the inscription. However, upon SEM examination of the spall, it was revealed to have detached along a natural crystal plane in the rock crystal. Thus, it is impossible to say whether the spall was removed on purpose or not, but it is possible that the eventual defacement of the inscription by the spall led to the discard of the amulet seal by its original users. This artifact is classed as an "amulet seal" because it belongs to a class of Islamic amulets with inscriptions written backward, just as one would on a stamp/cylinder seal. It is unlikely that this object was used as a seal because the inscription is so shallow. Rather, the inscription written backwards on this artifact could reflect a desire to preserve the magic of the amulet. Islamic amulets often display inscription written backwards. The writing on Islamic amulets usually mentions the name of God (Allah) or the name of the user, and many times is written backward or is composed of strings of letters that do not form words. The rock crystal material of the Unguja Ukuu amulet seal is in keeping with a class of Islamic amulet seals that were associated with rain-making magic. Rock crystal is associated in Islam with the waters of heaven, and thus forms an important material from which amulets and other religious objects are made. The source of the rock crystal used to make the amulet remains unknown as rock crystal cannot be traced chemically. The discovery of this amulet in what was an ancient garbage dump or midden remains inexplicable, as such sacred objects are often deposited in ritually important spaces, like mosque courtyards or cemeteries. Its discovery in a midden could indicate that it was lost unintentionally by its user.

Date Range: 700 CE - 900 CE

Region: Unguja Ukuu (Zanzibar)

Region tags: Africa, Eastern Africa, Tanzania, Unguja

The site of Unguja Ukuu on the island of Unguja (Zanzibar) off the Tanzanian coast.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Sarathi, Akshay, J. Mark Kenoyer, and Jonathan R. Walz. “An Early Islamic Rock Crystal Amulet Seal from Unguja Ukuu, Zanzibar” 20, no. 2 (April 13, 2022). <https://doi.org/10.1163/21915784-bja10013>.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: None

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: None

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Incised or Inscribed

Method of inscription

- Other [specify]: Rotary tool

Notes: The inscription was made in the rock crystal amulet seal using a rotary tool, likely like those employed by Near Eastern craftspeople in the 8th-9th centuries CE.

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Stone

Notes: The material of the amulet seal is rock crystal.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

- Physical preparation

Notes: A piece of rock crystal was broken off a larger piece and shaped into a cabochon before the inscription was made on the domed surface.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

- Physical preparation

Notes: There may have been physical preparation of the surface on which the inscription was to be made. There may have been ritual preparation associated with the making of this rock crystal amulet seal, but this is unknown.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– I don't know

Notes: The amulet seal was likely worn on one's person, set in jewelry, as indicated by the faint discoloration on its flat surface.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– I don't know

Notes: The amulet seal was likely worn on one's person, set in jewelry, as indicated by the faint discoloration on its flat surface. It is unknown whether the amulet seal was stored in association with other iconography of images. If this amulet seal was worn by an early convert to Islam on Zanzibar, it is possible that the syncretic nature of Swahili Islam did not preclude the use of other iconography or images. However, this remains unknown.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– I don't know

Notes: The amulet seal was likely worn on one's person, set in jewelry, as indicated by the faint discoloration on its flat surface. It could have been associated with aniconic images, but this remains unknown.

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– I don't know

Notes: The production of the rock crystal amulet could have been sponsored by a political entity. However, given that it was likely worn on someone's person, one cannot discount the possibility that it was produced for personal use and paid for by an individual.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: The inscription consists of a single Arabic word - "lillah" (for God). While the word has religious connotations, it cannot be considered official religious scripture due to its length and the commonality of the phrase.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– Yes

Notes: The word is inscribed in the Kufic script of Arabic, which remains in use to the present in the production of amulets and religious charms in Islam.

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

Notes: Arabic is the sacred language of Islam, and the Kufic script is often used for the production of amulets and religious objects.

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– No

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– No

Notes: The inscription consists of a single Arabic word, "lillah", which means "for God".

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– Yes

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals?

– No

Notes: Arabic is certainly the sacred language of Islam, but it has non-religious uses as well.

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Institutions

– Other [specify]: Theology

Notes: Muslim theology maintains that the Quran must be recited in Quranic Arabic. The manufacture of Islamic amulets employed Arabic for its magico-religious association.

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– Yes

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– Yes

Notes: Non-Arabic texts on Islam exist and circulate to this day.

Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Multiple oral traditions support the sacred status of Arabic in Islam.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– I don't know

Notes: This depends on how many Muslims were present at the site of Unguja Ukuu in the 8th-9th centuries, and how far beyond the Muslim World the owner of the amulet seal traveled. The number of people who would have found the amulet significant in any space would depend on a variety of factors, not least the composition and beliefs of local religious communities.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

– Yes

Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

Notes: The inscription merely says "lillah" ("for God"). However, other sacred texts in Islam encourage proselytizing.

Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– No

Notes: The inscription merely says "lillah" ("for God"). However, other sacred texts in Islam encourage proselytizing.

Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– No

Notes: The inscription merely says "lillah" ("for God"). However, other sacred texts in Islam encourage proselytizing.

Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– No

Notes: The inscription merely says "lillah" ("for God"). However, other sacred texts in Islam

encourage proselytizing by force.

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?

– Yes

Notes: Proselytizing is directed toward non-Muslims.

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– Yes

↳ Does proselytization take place regardless of the fact that the text is silent on the matter?

– Yes

Notes: The inscription merely says "lillah" ("for God"). However, other sacred texts in Islam encourage proselytizing.

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Notes: The inscription merely says "lillah" ("for God"). However, other sacred texts in Islam encourage proselytizing.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: Islam has had multiple reformist movements over the course of its history.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

↳ Is it orally recited?

– I don't know

Notes: The inscribed word on the amulet seal, "lillah" ("for God") could have been recited by its wearer.

↳ Is it read?

– I don't know

Notes: The inscribed word on the amulet seal, "lillah" ("for God") could have been read at times by its wearer.

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: The amulet seal was likely worn by a pious Muslim to invoke the name of God. However, rock crystal amulet seals with inscriptions in the reverse are often used in rain-summoning rituals in Islamic magic. Whether this amulet seal was used in such a capacity remains unknown.

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– I don't know

Notes: The amulet seal was likely worn by a pious Muslim to invoke the name of God. However, rock crystal amulet seals with inscriptions in the reverse are often used in rain-summoning rituals in Islamic magic. Whether this amulet seal was used in such a capacity - and the size of such rituals - remains unknown.

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– I don't know

Notes: The amulet seal was likely worn by a pious Muslim to invoke the name of God. However, rock crystal amulet seals with inscriptions in the reverse are often used in rain-summoning rituals in Islamic magic. Whether this amulet seal was used in such a capacity - and the size of such rituals - remains unknown.

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– I don't know

Notes: The frequency of rain-making rituals in the past remains unknown, assuming that this amulet seal was used in such rituals.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– I don't know

Notes: Islamic magic remains on the fringes of orthodox Islam in Zanzibar at present. While religious authorities are not happy with the practice of magic, it seems to take place with or without their blessing.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– I don't know

Notes: Islamic magic remains on the fringes of orthodox Islam in Zanzibar at present. While religious authorities are not happy with the practice of magic, it seems to take place with or without their blessing.

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– I don't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– I don't know

Notes: Given the syncretic nature of early East African Islam, it is possible that intoxicants or mind-altering substances were consumed in rituals associated with the amulet seal. However, this remains unknown.

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– I don't know

Notes: Food and drink could have been consumed in rain-making rituals in the past, assuming that this amulet seal was used in such rituals.

Is there material significance to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is it visible?

– Yes

Notes: It is carved on the domed surface of the amulet seal cabochon and likely set in jewelry worn on one's person. It was likely visible to all.

↳ Is it hidden?

– No

Notes: It is carved on the domed surface of the amulet seal cabochon and likely set in jewelry worn on one's person. It was likely visible to all.

↳ Can it be touched?

– Yes

Notes: It is carved on the domed surface of the amulet seal cabochon and likely set in jewelry worn on one's person. The text can be touched. However, regular touching may have caused the removal of a diagonal spall from across the surface of the inscription. This may have led to the abandonment of the amulet seal in a midden.

↳ Does touching the text during ritual have a specific function?

– I don't know

Notes: Touching the inscription or the amulet itself could have had magical or ritual significance. However, this remains unknown in the past East African context of amulet seal use.

↳ Does the material significance have an esoteric function?

– Yes

Notes: The rock crystal material of the amulet seal could have had association with rain-making rituals rooted in Islamic magic.

↳ Promotes knowledge?

– I don't know

Notes: The amulet could have been used to promote Islamic knowledge of some kind.

↳ Does the text serve a protective function?

– I don't know

Notes: The rock crystal amulet seal with its association inscription could have served a protective function.

↳ Does the text serve a healing function?

– I don't know

Notes: The rock crystal amulet seal with its association inscription could have served a healing function.

↳ Does the text serve a cleansing function?

– I don't know

Notes: The rock crystal amulet seal with its association inscription could have served a cleansing function.

↳ Does the text serve as a form of expiation?

– I don't know

Notes: The rock crystal amulet seal with its association inscription could have served a expiatory function.

↳ Does the text serve as an incantation?

– I don't know

Notes: The rock crystal amulet seal with its association inscription could have served an incantation repeated by the wearer.

↳ Has the materiality of the text been altered?

– Yes

↳ Specify

–Specify: At some point during the life history of the rock crystal amulet seal, a diagonal spall was removed across the surface of the inscription. At first, the excavators assumed that the spall represented a purposeful defacement of the inscription. However, upon inspecting it with SEM, it was determined that the spall was removed along a natural fault in the rock crystal. Whether this was purposeful or simply gradually widened until the inscription was damaged remains unknown.

↳ Are there debates about whether or not altering the materiality of the text is acceptable?

– I don't know

Notes: But there remains uncertainty concerning whether the diagonal spall removed across the inscription was purposeful or a result of a natural fault that grew in the rock crystal material of the amulet.

↳ Other important aspects of materiality with regard to the text?

– Yes

↳ Specify

–Specify: The rock crystal material has significance in Islam due to its associations with the waters of heaven. Rock crystal amulet seals are also used in Islamic magic in rain-making rituals. Whether this amulet seal was used in such a capacity remains unknown.

↳ Are there material substance that commonly accompany the text?

Please specify the substances in the sub-questions

– No

Notes: But the opposite is true - rock crystal amulets are always inscribed with phrases sacred to Islam.

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– I don't know

Notes: The inscription occurs on the domed surface of a rock crystal amulet, which was likely set in jewelry worn on one's person. Art could have associated with this jewelry or the amulet, especially given the syncretic nature of early East African Islam, in which multiple religious traditions came together.

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

Notes: The current text dates to the 8th-9th centuries CE. There are multiple inscriptions of this word ("lillah") that occur across multiple media in Islam.

↳ Content of text?

– No

Notes: The word "lillah" remains fairly stable across media and over time.

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– Yes

Notes: This particular amulet seal with the word "lillah" inscribed on it may have been used as a good luck charm or deployed in rain-making rituals. The different media across this word appears over time could have served different purposes.

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Notes: The word appears by itself on this amulet seal and others. However, the word does have Quranic implications.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: The word appears commonly in Islamic amulets. The word does have Quranic implications, however.

↳ Behavioral literature?

– I don't know

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: This is a common word to be inscribed on Islamic amulets.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: None

Notes: The inscription consists of a single word - "lillah" ("for God") inscribed on a rock crystal cabochon. It is strongly linked to Quranic traditions

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Notes: The inscription consists of a single word - "lillah" ("for God") inscribed on a rock crystal cabochon

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Notes: The inscription consists of a single word - "lillah" ("for God") inscribed on a rock crystal cabochon

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: The inscription consists of a single word - "lillah" ("for God") inscribed on a rock crystal cabochon

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Notes: The inscription consists of a single word - "lillah" ("for God") inscribed on a rock crystal cabochon

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Notes: The inscription consists of a single word - "lillah" ("for God") inscribed on a rock crystal cabochon

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Notes: The inscription consists of a single word - "lillah" ("for God") inscribed on a rock crystal cabochon

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Notes: The inscription consists of a single word - "lillah" ("for God") inscribed on a rock crystal cabochon

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Notes: The inscription consists of a single word - "lillah" ("for God") inscribed on a rock crystal cabochon

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Notes: The inscription consists of a single word - "lillah" ("for God") inscribed on a rock crystal cabochon

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Notes: The inscription consists of a single word - "lillah" ("for God") inscribed on a rock crystal cabochon

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Notes: The inscription consists of a single word - "lillah" ("for God") inscribed on a rock crystal cabochon

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: The single word of the text mentions Allah, the Muslim God.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
 - Yes
- ↳ Other features of the supreme high god
 - Specify: Beneficent, merciful, eternal, most sacred, embodiment of peace, infuser of faith, preserver of safety, might, omnipotent, dominant, creator, evolver, flawless, shaper, great forgiver, all-prevailing, supreme bestower, total provider, supreme solver, omniscient, the elevating one, honor-bestower, abaser, all-hearer, impartial judge, embodiment of justice, knower of subtleties, clement, magnificent, sublime, great, guardian, sustainer, reckoner, majestic, bountiful, watchful, responsive, omnipresent, wise, loving, glorious, infuser of life, all-observing, embodiment of truth, universal trustee, strong, firm, protective, singly laudable, the one to whom the count of all things are known, originator, restorer, maintainer of life, inflictor of death, self-subsisting, perceptive, all-noble, sole god, all-authoritative, expediter, delayer, first, perceptible, imperceptible, exalted, merciful, retaliator, pardoner, benign, sovereign, majestic, honorable, just, gatherer of creation, self-sufficient, distressor, bestower of sufficiency, preventer, bestower of benefits, prime light, provider of guidance, unique, ever-surviving, eternal inheritor, guide to path of rectitude, extensively enduring
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No
 - Notes: Omniscient

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Notes: Omniscient

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Notes: Omniscient

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region

– Yes

Notes: Omniscient

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Notes: Omniscient

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Notes: Omniscient

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Notes: Omniscient

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Notes: Omniscient

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Notes: Omniscient

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: Omniscient

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Can reward
– Yes

↳ Can punish
– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
– Yes
Notes: Direct causal efficacy as well.

↳ Exhibits positive emotion
– Yes

↳ Exhibits negative emotion
– Yes

↳ Possesses Hunger?
– No

↳ Can be hurt?
– No

↳ Can be tricked?
– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
– Specify: Beneficent, merciful, eternal, most sacred, embodiment of peace, infuser of faith, preserver of safety, might, omnipotent, dominant, creator, evolver, flawless, shaper, great forgiver, all-prevailing, supreme bestower, total provider, supreme solver,

omniscient, the elevating one, honor-bestower, abaser, all-hearer, impartial judge, embodiment of justice, knower of subtleties, clement, magnificent, sublime, great, guardian, sustainer, reckoner, majestic, bountiful, watchful, responsive, omnipresent, wise, loving, glorious, infuser of life, all-observing, embodiment of truth, universal trustee, strong, firm, protective, singly laudable, the one to whom the count of all things are known, originator, restorer, maintainer of life, inflictor of death, self-subsisting, perceptive, all-noble, sole god, all-authoritative, expediter, delayer, first, perceptible, imperceptible, exalted, merciful, retaliator, pardoner, benign, sovereign, majestic, honorable, just, gatherer of creation, self-sufficient, distressor, bestower of sufficiency, preventer, bestower of benefits, prime light, provider of guidance, unique, ever-surviving, eternal inheritor, guide to path of rectitude, extensively enduring

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– I don't know

Notes: It depends on how Muslim God would have been perceived by the wearer of the amulet.

↳ In dreams

– I don't know

Notes: It depends on how Muslim God would have been perceived by the wearer of the amulet.

↳ In trance possession

– I don't know

Notes: It depends on how Muslim God would have been perceived by the wearer of the amulet. Trance possessions are common in East African Islam.

↳ Through divination practices

– I don't know

Notes: It depends on how Muslim God would have been perceived by the wearer of the amulet. The amulet could have been used for rain-making rituals and/or divination. Divination remains an important part of the syncretized form of Islam practiced in East Africa.

↳ Only through religious specialists

– I don't know

Notes: It depends on how Muslim God would have been perceived by the wearer of the amulet. Religious and non-religious folk have access to Allah, depending on whom you ask in East Africa.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Notes: Inspiration, through recitation of Quran, through His prophets.

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– I don't know

Notes: It depends on how Muslim God would have been perceived by the wearer of the amulet.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Notes: The amulet only mention the Muslim God, Allah.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– I don't know

Notes: It depends on how Muslim God would have been perceived by the wearer of the amulet. The amulet only mention the Muslim God, Allah.

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– I don't know

Notes: It depends on how Muslim God would have been perceived by the wearer of the amulet. It is difficult to answer this question in the context of the syncretized forms of Islam present in East Africa. The amulet only mention the Muslim God, Allah.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Notes: Allah is omniscient.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Notes: Allah is omniscient.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Notes: Allah is omniscient.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

Notes: Allah is omniscient.

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Notes: Allah is omniscient.

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Notes: Allah is omniscient.

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Notes: Allah is omniscient.

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Notes: Allah is omniscient.

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Notes: Allah is omniscient.

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: Allah is omniscient.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

Notes: Not according to this text, but Allah is considered to communicate with the living in a variety of ways according to other Islamic texts and traditions.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: Allah has both direct and indirect causal efficacy in the world.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– I don't know

Notes: Allah can punish people, but whether is a consequence of negative emotion remains unknown to me.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

Notes: Allah is self-sufficient

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: Beneficent, merciful, eternal, most sacred, embodiment of peace, infuser of faith, preserver of safety, might, omnipotent, dominant, creator, evolver, flawless, shaper, great forgiver, all-prevailing, supreme bestower, total provider, supreme solver, omniscient, the elevating one, honor-bestower, abaser, all-hearer, impartial judge, embodiment of justice, knower of subtleties, clement, magnificent, sublime, great, guardian, sustainer, reckoner, majestic, bountiful, watchful, responsive, omnipresent, wise, loving, glorious, infuser of life, all-observing, embodiment of truth, universal trustee, strong, firm, protective, singly laudable, the one to whom the count of all things are known, originator, restorer, maintainer of life, inflictor of death, self-subsisting, perceptive, all-noble, sole god, all-authoritative, expediter, delayer, first, perceptible, imperceptible, exalted, merciful, retaliator, pardoner, benign, sovereign, majestic, honorable, just, gatherer of creation, self-sufficient, distressor, bestower of sufficiency, preventer, bestower of benefits, prime light, provider of guidance, unique, ever-surviving, eternal inheritor, guide to path of rectitude, extensively enduring

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Notes: The amulet only mentions Allah

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Notes: The amulet only mentions Allah

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– I don't know

Notes: It depends on how Muslim God would have been perceived by the wearer of the amulet. It is difficult to answer this question in the context of the syncretized forms of Islam present in East Africa.

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: No other categories of beings other than Allah are present in this text. Other Islamic textual traditions mention categories of beings other than humans and Allah, however. These include djinns and angels.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– I don't know

Notes: It depends on how Muslim God would have been perceived by the wearer of the amulet. It is difficult to answer this question in the context of the syncretized forms of Islam present in East Africa. The amulet may have been used in rain-making rituals given that it is of rock crystal.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– I don't know

Notes: It depends on how Muslim God would have been perceived by the wearer of the amulet. It is difficult to answer this question in the context of the syncretized forms of Islam present in East Africa. Supernatural monitoring could be implied by the mention of Allah.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: Not on the amulet, but Allah's divine punishment is mentioned in other Islamic texts and traditions.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: Not according to the text of this amulet, but Allah rewards humans in other Islamic texts and

traditions.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Notes: The amulet does not mention messianic beliefs, but there are Messianic traditions present in Islam.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Notes: The amulet does not mention eschatological traditions, but these are present in Islam as described in other Islamic texts and traditions.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Notes: The amulet only invokes the name of God in one word - "Lillah", which means "for God" in Arabic.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Notes: The amulet only invokes the name of God in one word - "Lillah", which means "for God" in Arabic.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– No

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– No

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– No

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

Notes: With the word, "Lillah", ("for God"), the amulet's text could be a pious expression of religious righteousness.

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– No

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

Notes: With the word, "Lillah", ("for God"), the amulet's text could be a pious expression of respect for Allah.

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– No

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

Notes: With the word, "Lillah", ("for God"), the amulet's text could be a pious expression of religious fidelity/loyalty to Allah.

↳ Cooperation

– No

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– No

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– No

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

↳ Humility/modesty

– I don't know

Notes: With the word, "Lillah", ("for God"), the amulet's text could be a pious expression of humility/modesty before the divine.

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– No

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– I don't know

Notes: With the word, "Lillah", ("for God"), the amulet's text could be a pious expression of gratitude/thankfulness to the Divine.

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– I don't know

Notes: With the word, "Lillah", ("for God"), the amulet's text could be a pious expression of reverence/awe/wonder for the Divine.

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

Notes: With the word, "Lillah", ("for God"), the amulet's text could be a pious expression of religious faith/belief/trust/devotion in/to Allah.

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– No

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– No

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

↳ Other important virtues

– No

– I don't know

Notes: It is possible that any or all of these virtues were at least implied by the amulet's text for its wearer.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: The amulet only has a single word - "Lillah", ("for God") carved on it.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: The amulet only has a single word - "Lillah", ("for God") carved on it.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Notes: The amulet only has a single word - "Lillah", ("for God") carved on it.

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Notes: The amulet only has a single word - "Lillah", ("for God") carved on it.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Notes: But other texts in Islam do mention taboos on certain foods.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Notes: The amulet only has a single word - "Lillah", ("for God") carved on it. This could be understood to mean accepting the ethical precepts associated with Islam.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification?

– No

↳ Circumcision?

– No

↳ Food taboos?

– No

↳ Hair?

– No

↳ Dress?

– No

↳ Ornaments?

– Yes

Notes: The amulet itself is a rock crystal ornament that would have been worn on one's person as an expression of piety, but also as a signal that one had access to materials like rock crystal.

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– Yes

Notes: The inscription on the amulet is written in angular Kufic, a script with ritual and magical significance in Islam.

↳ Other?

– Specify: None

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Notes: The amulet was likely produced in the Near East during the 8th-9th centuries CE, when the Islamic caliphates had conquered a region stretching from India in the east to Spain in the west.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Notes: The amulet was likely produced in the Near East during the 8th-9th centuries CE, when the Islamic caliphates had conquered a region stretching from India in the east to Spain in the west. There were likely specialist craftspersons in the new Islamic empire that controlled the production of amulets and charms associated with Islam.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: The removal of the diagonal spall across the writing on the amulet is puzzling. It could be either the product of a natural fault opening in the rock crystal, or it could be natural. Why the text would have been defaced and then deposited in a garbage midden is unknown, as this goes against accepted Muslim practice.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: Madrassas would have existed in the Muslim world (probably not in Unguja Ukuu at the time of the production and use of the amulet) that would have existed to teach people (especially men) Arabic and the precepts of Islam.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: Education in the Islamic world has traditionally been reserved for men but with significant exceptions.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Unguja Ukuu Amulet Seal, Sarathi, Akshay, J. Mark Kenoyer, and Jonathan R. Walz. "An Early Islamic Rock Crystal Amulet Seal from Unguja Ukuu, Zanzibar" 20, no. 2 (April 13, 2022). <https://doi.org/10.1163/21915784-bja10013>.